

**AN EVALUATION OF THE IMPLICATIONS OF INTRA-URBAN
MIGRATION ON RESIDENTIAL REAL ESTATE MARKET IN ASABA,
DELTA STATE, NIGERIA.**

¹Bernard Adjekophori, ²Fidelis, I, Emoh, ³Monday Osagioduwa
Email: benejis@gmail.com, emohf@ub.ac.bw, wilosag@yahoo.com

¹Department of Estate Management and Valuation, Auchi Polytechnic Auchi, Edo State, Nigeria

²Department of Architecture and Planning, University of Botswana, Gaborone, Botswana

³Department of Urban and Regional Planning, University of Benin, Edo State, Nigeria

Corresponding Author's Email: benejis@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

Migration dynamics remain one of the daunting hydra-headed challenges confronting contemporary African cities in the 21st century. This study investigates the implications of intra-urban migration on residential real estate market with a view to ascertaining the factors influencing intra-urban migrations and the extent to which it affects residential real estate submarket in Asaba, Nigeria. The study adopted a descriptive research design. A 5-point Likert scale questionnaire was developed and administered on 133 participants which comprise of 121 household head and 12 registered Estate Surveyors and Valuers firm in the city of Asaba. The systematic, random and purposive sampling techniques were used in the selection of the participants. Data collected were captured in statistical package for social science (SPSS Version 23) and were analyzed using Relative Impact Index (RII) and Factor Analysis (FA). Results of the study found that social environment, accessibility, employment were the major factors influencing intra-urban movement. It also discovered that deterioration of infrastructural facilities as a result of over population, increase in the demand for residential property and increase the level of urban consumption were the most important effects of intra-urban migration on Asaba residential submarket. The study therefore recommends that governments at all level should provide social infrastructures and employment opportunities to improve the quality of life and discourage intra-urban movement within the city. Investors should take advantage of the situation and invest heavily in residential real estate in other to secure maximum return on investment. States and local government should get ready with better strategies to increase housing supply and infrastructural provision and improvement in strategic location around the city to control the level of intra-urban migration in Asaba

Keywords: Asaba, Intra-Urban, Migration, Real estate; Residential submarket

1. Introduction

Migration has been and will continue to be one of the major drivers of urban growth the world over. It is estimated about 55% of the world population is currently living in the cities and this is expected to reach about 68% by 2050. (Asad et. al., 2022; Ritchie & Roser,2020; Aerni, 2016; International Organization of Migration (IOM), 2015). Migration is considered as the movement of people from one geographical region to another, which may be on temporary or permanent basis (Adewale, 2005; Amrevurayire & Ojeh, 2016). Migrants are all those who have left their usual place of residence, regardless of the reason for migration, their legal status or duration of absence (Carling, 2019). Li and Dodson (2022) noted that intra-urban migration is an important category of internal migration that relocates human and social capital in urban areas, contributing to changes in urban residential and labour market structure.

Migration comes in different types and pattern, which could be voluntary or induced, internal or external, rural or urban as the case may be, and each of them with its associated challenges. Migration according to Amrevurayire and Ojeh, (2016) is a selective process affecting individuals or families with certain economic, social, educational and demographic characteristics. Globally, there is an increase in the number of people moving from one geographical location to another and this will continue to generate problem of different kinds especially in demand for affordable and fair housing to the destination of the migrants (Asad et. al., 2022; Ayab-Karlsson et. al. 2018; World Economic Forum, 2017). Migration within cities can create socio-economic and environmental issues like urban poverty, urban slum, urban housing and infrastructural challenges.

There are many factors that affect household's decision to move, such as; better housing quality, school quality, a better neighborhood, increased accessibility, a change of housing tenure, and other job-related reasons (Chien-Wen & I-Chun, 2019). When the moving distance is shorter, the reasons for moving are more housing-related. (Jones, Leishman & Watkins, 2004; Peng, Wu, & Kung, 2009; Ermisch & Washbrook, 2012). When the moving distance is longer, the reasons for moving are more job-related (Berger & Blomquist, 1992; Gabriel, Shack-Marquez, & Wascher, 1992; Potepan, 1994; Zabel, 2012). Adedeji (2013), noted that the factors forcing families to change their place of residence in the city, is subject to the desires, ambitions and expectations which in itself is a subject to the family status, education, income, lifestyle and the dwelling condition of these families. In addition, physical quality, accessibility to the public services and infrastructures, social amenities of various neighborhoods are among the attracting and repelling factors that play a significant role in the intra urban movements.

Migration has become one of the most pressing social, economic and political issues, generating heated debates in countries facing large influxes of immigrants (Saiz & Wachter, 2011; Accetturo, Manaresi, Mocetti, & Olivieri, 2014; Barometz & Boustan, 2017). Intra-urban migration is normally viewed as short distance intra-community moves within city spaces (Clark, 2008). At the individual level, intra-urban residential mobility has been re-conceptualized as relational practices that link lives through time, multi-locality and space while connecting people to structural conditions (Weichhart, 2015; Coulter, Ham & Findlay, 2016). Evidence shows that choice to

change a location is influenced by the individuals' satisfaction or dissatisfaction with respect to utilities in a given location (Bwambale, Bukuluki, Moyer & Borne, 2021). Many factors may be attributable to intra-urban migration in one region but may not be applicable in other regions. Additionally, households in developing countries have their own peculiar reasons for relocating within the same city which may be quite different from what is obtainable in developed countries (Ajibuah, 2010). According to Adedeji (2013), families' movement from one neighborhood to another neighborhood inside the cities brings up obvious consequences on the formation and changing social domain inside the cities and generally on the social spatial structure of the cities.

Several studies on various aspect of migration and its associated challenges and prospects on housing generally has been advanced by academics, professionals and researchers at both national and international level. For instance, Yanoti *et. al.* (2024) conducted a study on house price dynamics and internal migration across Australia and discovered that internal migration is a determinant of housing price from region to region. The study of Gala (2024) also testify to the fact that there is correlation between migration and house price across different regions in Canada. Again, Partridge *et.al.* (2010), noted that high migrants in certain region of United State led to an increase in housing price and rent. Erol and Unal (2022) observed that internal migration increases total population and its associated house price. Yingchao, Zhili, Weiyan and Jing (2018), examine the impact of migration on urban housing price in China and found that population inflow has a positive correlation with urban housing price on the national, regional and eastern region, but it has no impact on urban housing price in the central and western region. Chien-Wen, and I-Chun (2019), examine the long- and short-run influences of migration on housing prices in Taiwan and the study revealed that migration and housing prices are cointegrated, and the influence of migration on housing prices is significantly positive in the long run. However, the influence of migration on housing price is not as significant as expected in the short run. These studies focus mainly on international migration and housing price leaving the research that estimates the effects of intra-urban migration on residential property value undone. Gugler (1991), conducted a study on an assessment of changes in urban-rural ties in Anambra state and found that many Igbo families encouraged their family members to migrate because of the belief that their continued stay in the village will not bring financial success. Moreover, a study carried out in Aba, southeastern Nigeria, focused only on rural-urban interactions without examining the migratory processes that yielded the interactions (Chukwuezi, 1999). Chukwuedozie and Patience (2013), examine the effects of rural-urban migration on rural communities of southeastern Nigeria and found that rural-urban migration contributes significantly towards the development of their rural communities and increase housing demand. Despite plethora of studies on this issue and the correlational evidences of migration and housing prices and rent, there is still dearth of researches on the effects intra-urban migration and real estate market in the south-south region and particularly in Asaba, a fast-growing city with high rate of internal and external movement. This therefore creates a research gap that motivate this study and make it significant to investigate the implications of intra-urban migration on residential real estate market. The objective of the paper therefore is to empirically ascertain, using factor analytical approach and relative impact index, the major factors influencing intra-urban movement and the effects it may have on residential real estate market in Asaba, Nigeria.

2 Literature Review

The Concept of Migration

Since the earliest times, humanity has been on the move. Some people move in search of work or economic opportunities, to join family, or to study. Others move to escape conflict, persecution, terrorism, or human rights violations. Still others move in response to the adverse effects of climate change, natural disasters, or other environmental factors. (Vincent, 2022). Migrants are all those who have left their usual place of residence, regardless of the reason for migration, their legal status or duration of absence (Carling, 2019). Migration is the movement of people from one place, locality or country to another. Vincent (2022) citing Ghosh (2006), considers migration as a change of place of living for almost as a long stable period. The causes of migration are numerous ranging from natural calamities, climate change, epidemics, drought, socio-economic, cultural and political upheaval to the issue of over population. Heavy pressure on resources may be the cause of permanent or temporary and long distance or short distance migration.

Empirical studies of Factors influencing Migration

Literature in the academic writing has dealt with the question of how migration affects migrants and their households staying back in areas of origin, as well as communities and place of origin. This literature also helps us to understand the potential direct effects of migration on development housing education and other basic infrastructure and amenities.

Previous studies on this migration has stated that the effects of immigration on housing value are, at best, mild and occur over a longer time horizon (Haider & Moraines, 2019). Akbari & Ayodede (2013) estimated the effects of immigration on real estate prices using census data between 1996 and 2006. They found that the maximum increase in house prices caused by immigration is in the range of 0.10-0.12%, and this is caused by immigrants arriving over ten years before the effect. In the short term, immigrants have positive effects on local economies. Gala (2024) investigates the relationship between immigration and house prices in Canada using econometric methods, the results show that immigration, on average, has no significant effect on housing prices. The question of how migration affects development has been considered on both the macro- and micro-level. As noted by Andersson and Siegel (2019), migration generally affects development at five levels: (1) individual (e.g. migrants enjoying higher wages due to emigration); (2) household (e.g. increased education spending in the household staying back due to remittances); (3) community (e.g. increased demand for consumption goods due to remittances being spent in the community); (4) regional economy and (5) global economy (e.g. more efficient allocation of labour regionally and globally).

Emmanuel, Yusoff and Musa (2015) identified some factors as influential in determining the choice of new locations or residence by households. They include;

Social environment: Environment with neighbourhood prestige, socio-economic, ethnic, and demographic composition will attract people and make them move to such environment.

Physical characteristics of neighbourhood: Physical condition of street and sidewalk, layout of street patterns, quietness, privacy, spaciousness, and beauty of the locale also influencing intra-urban migrations. People will tend to leave a neighbourhood without good physical characteristic to a neighbourhood with good physical characteristics.

Accessibility: Neighbourhood with easy proximity to the CBD, major highways, public transportation to place of work, shopping centres, schools, and recreational area will tend to attract people as individuals will love to live in an environment with good accessibility and this will make them leave their present place of residence which suffer inaccessibility.

Services and facilities: The quality of public utility services, schools, police and fire protection, and home delivery services in a neighbourhood will attract people with inadequate public utility in their neighbourhood thereby leading to intra-urban migration.

Individual site and dwelling characteristics: Property with low maintenance costs, big plot size, spatial configuration, big house size, good design and in good state of repair will attract people and make them to migrate to such property.

Personal characteristics: People migrate for personal reason. This could be because they are not happy with the situation they found themselves at that point in life and found themselves in despair, angry and frustrated because they lost the life he used to live. Migration for these participants was a way to escape from all these unpleasant happenings in their lives.

Employment and occupation considerations: People may migrate because they are unemployed and despite job hunting, were unsuccessful due to very limited job opportunities they will see a need to migrate, which is the only hope to transform their lives and family members.

Identifying with ethnic or racial kith and religious affiliations: People who live in an environment that does not identify with ethnic or religious affiliation may also tend to migrate to an environment where there are people with similar religion, ethnic and racial kith.

Economic status: People with higher economic status who live in an environment of lower economic status may be forced to move to an environment where people of his class or economic state reside.

Level of education: People with higher level of education may relocate to a different environment where they can meet or relate with people in the same class of education with them.

Vincent (2022) avowed that one of the prime reasons for migration is the need for people to improve their economic condition. Thus, unemployment and poverty create room for people to desire better economic opportunities which motivates and forces some people to emigrate from their country of origin or place of residence.

Identified Gap in Literature Reviewed

Several studies on migration exist in literature. However, most focused on the type, determinant, causes, consequences and other aspect mainly in developed nation from the summary of the related past literature reviewed. It is observed that there is a dearth of studies on intra-urban type of migration and how it affects residential real estate submarket in emerging economies and specifically in Asaba the geographical scope for this study. Again, most of the past researches used secondary data and adopted theoretical and qualitative research technique, in their study. this research gap limits our understanding of the implications of internal movement to stakeholders such as government and real estate investors. This current study employed a different approach by using primary data and cross-sectional method. The study contributes to knowledge on using a

Factor analysis and relative impact index statistical tools to analyzing the factors that influence intra-urban migration and potential implications of residential property market in Asaba, Nigeria.

3. Research Method

The study's setting is Asaba, the capital city and administrative headquarter of Delta State in the South-South region of Nigeria. The city is located at the Western Bank of the Niger River with coordinate of 6°11'N 6°44'E. Asaba is one of the 3 towns of Oshimili South Local Government Area, a fast-developing urban area. Asaba had a population of 149,603 as at the 2006 census, and due to the influx of people to the administrative town and the rapid urban growth of the cities, Asaba is already estimated to be about 213,663 according to National Bureau of Statistics (2024). Asaba is well known for social activities due to the presence of physical and social and tourism amenities such as hotels, clubs, cinemas, malls, event centre, etc. Due to its large population, crimes such as pick pocketing, sideways robbery, etc., are rampant in the city. Cost of living is also on the high in Asaba. The Onitsha bridge is the boundary between Delta and Anambra state, as the bridge separates Asaba and Onitsha. Asaba is situated on a terrace of the lower Niger River, overlooking the point where the Anambra River flows into it. Beyond the river banks, on the high plains which are far more extensive than the river basins, secondary forest vegetation flourishes. The historic Niger River is a trans-African link beginning from West Africa and down into the Atlantic Ocean. Asaba forms a connector between western, eastern and northern Nigeria through the Niger River from the north and via the Asaba Niger Bridge, an east-west link and a Nigerian landmark. Asaba lies approximately 6°N of the equator and about the same distance east of the meridian; about 160 kilometers (100 mi) North of where the River Niger flows into the Atlantic Ocean. The greater Asaba occupies an area of about 300 square kilometers. It maintains an average tropical temperature of 32°C during the dry season and an average fertile rainfall of 2,700 millimeters (106 in) during the rainy season.

The need for empirical investigation of the implications of intra-urban migration on real estate market necessitated this study. Descriptive cum survey research design was adopted. This is a systematic process of gathering data about a situation, population or phenomenon without necessarily influencing the result. Primary data were used for the study. Through the administration of a well-structured 5-point Likert format, questionnaire was administered to 212 respondents comprising household head selected each from the eight quarters in Asaba namely: Umuezei, Umuonaje, Umuagu, Okwe, Ugbommanta, Ogbese, Umuaji and Ogbeilo and six firms of registered Estate Surveyors and Valuers domicile and practicing in Asaba. Each of the firm is represented with two Estate Surveyor and Valuers. 133 well completed questionnaire were retrieved representing 62.5% response rate which above average of 50% and therefore consider adequate for the analysis presented in this work. The data were gathered between March and August 2022. Both quantitative and qualitative data were collected concurrently and analyzed together (Creswell & Plano-Clark, 2018; Shakantu & Ibrahim, 2020, Adjekophori *et al*, 2022). One of the main considerations for selecting participant for the study was that such individual must have the knowledge of the study, and must be an adult residing in the study area for at least a period of 10 years. Cost and time are just two of the difficulties impeding the sampling of the entire

population (Ba-an, 2022). Thus, sampling was created to produce cost-effective yet accurate study findings (Singh, 2006; Ofori, 2020, Adjekophori *et al.*, 2024). A combination of systematic and purposive sampling techniques was employed in the actual selection of the sample. The Estate Surveyors and Valuers were purposively selected while the household head were systematically sampled. Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 23 was used to capture the data collected while Relative Importance Index (RII), and Factor Analysis (FA) were employed for the analysis. The data was measured on a 5-point Likert scale. The internal consistency and reliability were tested with Cronbach`s alpha @ 0.08, which is between the standard range of between 0.08 and 0.95 (Adjekophori *et. al.*, 2022a; Jamsen, 2021; Kolbediri & Sobhiyah, 2014). Meyer-Olkin (KMO) test and Bartlett`s sphericity test revealed there is high level of internal consistency among them at 0.682. Principal component analysis (PCA) was adopted to analyze information into the minimum number of factors by concentrating the explanatory power of the first factor (Rossoni, Engelbert & Bellegard, 2016; Adjekophori *et. al.*, 2022a). The next sub-heading presents the results of the study.

4.1 **Results and Discussion**

Table 1: Showing the factors influencing intra-urban migrations in Asaba.

S/N	Factors	RII	Rank
1	Social environment	0.88	1 st
2	Accessibility	0.86	2 nd
3	Employment and occupation considerations	0.85	3 rd
4	Physical characteristics of neighbourhood	0.84	4 th
5	Monthly household income	0.83	5 th
6	Neighbourhood services and facilities	0.82	6 th
7	Economic status	0.81	7 th
8	Cost of house rent	0.81	7 th
9	Better working conditions	0.81	7 th
10	Income	0.81	7 th
11	Social security	0.80	8 th
12	Proximity to workplace	0.79	9 th
13	Personal characteristics of the property	0.79	9 th
14	availability of house to rent	0.79	9 th
15	Location features	0.78	10 th
15	Individual site and dwelling characteristics	0.78	10 th
17	Convenience to access workplace	0.78	10 th
18	workplace location	0.77	11 th
19	Water availability	0.76	12 th
20	Distance to health facilities	0.76	12 th
21	Distance to bus routine and school	0.74	13 th
22	Family relations	0.74	13 th
23	The numbers of rooms	0.72	14 th
24	Household characteristics	0.71	15 th
25	Age of the building	0.71	15 th
26	Issuance of quit notice	0.71	15 th
27	Level of education	0.69	16 th

28	Identifying with ethnic/racial & religious affiliations	0.69	16 th
29	Room size	0.69	16 th
30	Size of dwelling unit	0.69	16 th
31	Government compulsory acquisition of property	0.68	17 th

Source: Field survey, 2022

Table 1 shows the factors influencing intra-urban migrations in Asaba. Findings revealed that social environment, accessibility and employment and occupation considerations were the major factors influencing intra-urban migrations in the study area. These are ranked 1st, 2nd and 3rd with a relative importance index of 0.88, 0.86 and 0.85 respectively. Their opinion could be because people migrate from one environment to another when the environment enjoys social environment, easy accessibilities and also when there are employment opportunities in such environment. Next in ranking are physical characteristics of neighbourhood, monthly household income and neighbourhood services and facilities. These were ranked 4th, 5th and 6th with a relative importance index of 0.84, 0.83 and 0.82 respectively. The least ranked factors influencing intra-urban migrations in the study area are household characteristics, age of the building, issuance of quit notice, level of education, identifying with ethnic or racial kith and religious affiliations, room size, size of dwelling unit, government compulsory acquisition of property. They were ranked 15th, 16th and 17th with a relative importance index of 0.71, 0.69 and 0.68 respectively. This affirms the studies of Louise *et al.*, (2017), Emmanuel, Yusoff and Musa (2015). Kyaing (2012), Yingchao *et al.*, (2018) Bwambale *et. al.* (2021) Adedokun and Karzanova, (2021) on the factors that influence migration in different region.

KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.632
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	1191.451
	Df	465
	Sig.	.000

The reliability test of responses determined through KMO and Bartlett's Test revealed that there is high level of internal consistent among the items at 0.682 Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy. This indicates that the data is suitable for further analysis and the opinion of respondents is considered suitable and reliable. The result of chi-square statistic (1191.451) at p-value (0.000) less than 0.05 level of significance revealed that the opinion of respondents on these factors are statistically and significantly related in other word the respondent strongly agreed that the factors influencing intra-urban migrations.

Table 2: Showing Total Variance Explained on the factors influencing intra-urban migrations in Asaba.

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	4.901	15.809	15.809	4.901	15.809	15.809	2.384	7.691	7.691
2	2.886	9.310	25.118	2.886	9.310	25.118	2.267	7.313	15.004
3	2.388	7.702	32.821	2.388	7.702	32.821	2.101	6.776	21.780
4	1.832	5.911	38.731	1.832	5.911	38.731	2.020	6.516	28.296
5	1.617	5.215	43.946	1.617	5.215	43.946	1.982	6.393	34.689
6	1.353	4.365	48.312	1.353	4.365	48.312	1.925	6.209	40.898
7	1.293	4.171	52.483	1.293	4.171	52.483	1.813	5.849	46.747
8	1.154	3.724	56.207	1.154	3.724	56.207	1.789	5.770	52.517
9	1.115	3.595	59.802	1.115	3.595	59.802	1.690	5.452	57.969
10	1.072	3.458	63.260	1.072	3.458	63.260	1.454	4.692	62.661
11	1.008	3.252	66.512	1.008	3.252	66.512	1.194	3.851	66.512
12	.959	3.093	69.605						
13	.952	3.071	72.676						
14	.870	2.806	75.483						
15	.778	2.509	77.991						
16	.726	2.341	80.332						
17	.691	2.228	82.560						
18	.640	2.065	84.626						
19	.590	1.904	86.529						
20	.530	1.709	88.239						
21	.501	1.616	89.855						
22	.468	1.508	91.363						
23	.435	1.405	92.768						
24	.410	1.323	94.091						
25	.351	1.132	95.223						
26	.322	1.039	96.262						
27	.282	.910	97.172						
28	.273	.879	98.051						
29	.226	.729	98.780						
30	.198	.639	99.419						
31	.180	.581	100.000						

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Table 2 shows the Total Variance Explained on the factors influencing intra-urban migrations in Asaba. The eigenvalue in the table, and the total under eigenvalue revealed the amount of total variance in the original variable accounted for by each of the components. The variance which is simply the ratio of variance accounted for by each of the component to the total variance of the variables. The extraction of sum of the square loadings in the second section explained the variability in the original 31 variables and out of which, eleven (11) factors were loaded. The extracted components explained 66.512% variability in the original variables. therefore, this study considerably reduces the data by selecting the extracted components as the most emphasized factors or components with the minimum of 33.488% loss of information. This further indicates that the outlined determinant the factors that influencing intra-urban migrations in Asaba are through representative of entire reasons.

Table 3 Loading analysis of the factors that influencing intra-urban migrations in Asaba

FACTORS	FACTOR LOADIN G	EIGENVAL UE	% OF VARIANC E
FACTOR 1: Accessibility and cost factor		4.901	15.809
Availability of house to rent	.767		
Proximity to workplace	.716		
Workplace location	.508		
Monthly household income	.732		
Income	.643		
Cost of house rent	.525		
FACTOR 2: Locational and property factor		2.886	9.310
Location features	.657		
Social environment	.618		
Water availability	.540		
FACTOR 3: Property and public factor		2.388	7.702
Personal characteristics of the property	.930		
Age of the building	.772		
Government compulsory acquisition of properties	.760		
Issuance of quit notice	.602		
FACTOR 4: Physical and neighbourhood factor		1.832	5.911
Neighbourhood services and facilities	.826		
Accessibility	.571		
Physical characteristics of neighbourhood	.518		
FACTOR 5: Household safety factor		1.617	5.215
Social security	.794		

Better working conditions	.752		
FACTOR 6: Public facilities accessibility and family factor		1.353	4.365
Convenience to access workplace	-1.016		
Distance to health facilities	.746		
family relations	.738		
Distance to bus routine and school	.621		
FACTOR 7: Property design		1.293	4.171
The numbers of rooms	.773		
Room size	.686		
FACTOR 8: Individual factor		1.154	3.724
Individual site and dwelling characteristics	.700		
Level of education	.586		
Identifying with ethnic or racial kith and religious affiliations	.561		
FACTOR 9: Economical factor		1.115	3.595
Economic status	.840		
Employment and occupation considerations	-1.010		
FACTOR 10: Property size		1.072	3.458
Size of dwelling unit	.701		
FACTOR 11: Household factor		1.008	3.252
Household characteristics	.829		

Source: Field survey, 2022

Table 3 revealed the result of analysis of factors influencing intra-urban migrations in Asaba. A total of eleven (11) factors loaded. Factor one (1) is accessibility and cost factor which explained about 15.809% variance in the determinant factors that influence intra-urban migrations in Asaba. The accessibility and cost factor include availability of house to rent, proximity to workplace, workplace location, monthly household income, income and cost of house rent. The second (2) factors that influence intra-urban migrations are locational and property factor and it explained 9.310% variance, this locational and property factor include location features, social environment and water availability. Factor three (3) is named as property and public factor, and it explained 7.702% variance in the determinant factors influencing intra-urban migrations in the study area. Such property and public factor comprise of personal characteristics of the property, age of the building, government compulsory acquisition of properties and issuance of quit notice. Factor four (4) is named as physical and neighborhood factor and it explained 5.911% variance in the determinant factors that influence intra-urban migrations in the study area. Such physical and neighbourhood factor comprises of neighborhood services and facilities, accessibility and physical characteristics of neighbourhood. Factor five (5) is household safety factor and it explained 5.215% variance in the determinant the determinant factors that influence intra-urban migrations

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in the study area. Such household safety factor comprises of social security and better working conditions. Factor six (6) is public facilities accessibility and family factor and it explained 4.365% variance in the determinant factors that influence intra-urban migrations in the study area, such public facilities accessibility and family factor comprises of convenience to access workplace, distance to health facilities, family relations and distance to bus routine and school. Factor seven (7) is named as property design, and it explained 4.171% variance in the determinant factors influencing intra-urban migrations in the study area. Such property design comprises of the numbers of rooms and room size. Factor eight (8) is named individual factor and it explained 3.724% variance in the determinant factors that influence intra-urban migrations in the study area. Such individual factor comprises of individual site and dwelling characteristics, level of education and identifying with ethnic or racial kith and religious affiliations. Factor nine (9) is economical factor and it explained 3.595% variance in the determinant factors that influence intra-urban migrations in the study area. Such economical factor comprises of economic status and employment and occupation considerations. Factor ten (10) is property size and it explained 3.458% variance in the determinant factors that influence intra-urban migrations in the study area, such property size comprises of size of dwelling unit. Factor eleven (11) is household factor and it explained 3.252% variance in the determinant factors that influence intra-urban migrations in the study area, such household factor comprises of household characteristics.

Table 4.: Showing the extent to which intra-urban migration affects residential real estate market in the study area.

S/N	Effect	RII	Rank
1	Deterioration of infrastructural facilities as a result of over population.	0.82	1 st
2	Increase in the demand of residential property as a result of scarcity of residential property	0.81	2 nd
3	Increase the level of urban consumption	0.78	3 rd
4	Decrease in labour cost as a result of influx of labor force	0.74	4 th
5	Increase in labour cost as a result of the reduction in population of labor force	0.74	4 th
6	Improvement in the life span of infrastructural facilities as a result of over population.	0.74	4 th
7	Increases the level of urban economic development	0.71	5 th
8	Increase rental value of residential property	0.71	5 th
9	Increase the number of residential property supply	0.70	6 th
10	Decrease the number of residential property supply	0.67	7 th
11	Decrease rental value of residential property	0.65	8 th
12	Decrease in the demand of residential property	0.64	9 th
13	Decreases the level of urban economic development	0.63	10 th

Source: Field survey, 2022

Table 4.7 shows the extent to which intra-urban migration affects real estate investors in the study area. The table revealed deterioration of infrastructural facilities as a result of over population,

increase in the demand of residential property as a result of scarcity of residential property and increase the level of urban consumption were the most important effects of intra-urban migration on real estate investors in the study area. These are ranked 1st, 2nd and 3rd with relative importance index of 0.82, 0.81 and 0.78 respectively. Their opinion could be because intra-urban migration increases population which can lead to deterioration of infrastructural facilities, increase in the demand of residential property and increase in the level of urban consumption. Next in the ranking are decrease in labour cost as a result of influx of labor force, increase in labour cost as a result of the reduction in population of labor force, improvement in the life span of infrastructural facilities as a result of over population, increases the level of urban economic development, increase rental value of residential property and increase the number of residential property supply. These were ranked 4th, 5th and 6th with relative importance index of 0.74, 0.71 and 0.79 respectively. The least ranked effects of intra-urban migration on real estate investors in the study area are Decrease rental value of residential property, decrease in the demand of residential property and Decreases the level of urban economic development ranking 8th, 9th and 10th with relative importance index of 0.65, 0.64 and 0.63 respectively.

4.2 Discussion of findings

The first objective of this study was to ascertain the factors that influence intra-urban migration in the study area. Table 1 presents the results of the factors influencing intra-urban migrations in Asaba. Most of the participants avow that social environment, accessibility and employment and occupation considerations and physical characteristics of neighborhood were the major factors influencing intra-urban migrations in the study area with relative importance index of 0.88, 0.86, 0.85 and 0.84 respectively. This result is in conformity with findings of Louise *et al.*, (2017), Emmanuel, Yusoff and Musa (2015). It also affirms the submission of Kyaing (2012), Yingchao *et al.*, (2018) that socio-cultural, demographic and miscellaneous factors influence internal migration in rural area of Monywa township. This result also underscores the findings of Bwambale *et al.* (2021) that infrastructure induces movement from one neighborhood to another within a city. This again is a confirmation of the findings of Adedokun & Karzanova, (2021) that discovered that unemployment resulting to low standard of living influences intra-urban migration. The second objective was to determine the extent to which intra-urban migration affects residential real estate market in the study area, this is presented in table 4, the study revealed that deterioration of infrastructural facilities as a result of over population, increase in the demand of residential property as a result of scarcity of residential property and increase the level of urban consumption with relative impact index of 0.82, 0.81, 0.78 and 0.74 respectively, were the most important effects of intra-urban migration on residential real estate market in the study area. This finding is at variance with the studies of Yingchao, Zhili, Weiyan and Jing (2018), Rubin and Felsenstein, (2017), Sun and Gao, (2014) on the effect of intra-urban migration on residential property market. This study to a large extent conforms with previous studies results on the factors influencing migration, but contributed to knowledge in providing information on intra-urban migration in the study area which was lacking in literature. Despite the laudable results of our study, it is worth noting that the study's scope is limited to only Asaba, the capital of Delta state, and we also

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investigate only intra-urban movement, with relatively small sample size, therefore these may limit the generalization of the study's outcome. We therefore recommend future research to cover both intra and inter-urban migration and to also consider a larger sample and to also cover larger scope to give a further understanding of the implications of migration on real estate market in general.

5. Conclusion and Recommendation

This research effort empirically investigates the factors that influence intra-urban migration with a view to ascertaining its implications on Asaba residential real estate market. It was found that that social environment, accessibility, employment and occupation considerations were the major factors influencing intra-urban migrations in the study area. On the other hand, the study discovered that deterioration of infrastructural facilities as a result of over population, increase in the demand of residential property as a result of scarcity of residential property and increase the level of urban consumption were the most important effects of intra-urban migration on Asaba real estate market. The study therefore recommends that real estate investors in the study area should take advantage of the intra-urban movement and invest massively in residential property of different class as increase of population in different submarket will invariably led to increase in demand for residential property thereby increasing the rental value of residential property and higher return on investment for the investors. Since the city fringe is receiving internal movement, there is need for the State and local government to get ready with better strategies to increase housing supply and infrastructural provision and improvement in strategic location around the city, this will discourage the movement of people to one direction either for social, employment of occupational reasons. There is also need for the alignment of government policies for housing, infrastructural and amenities provision, employment as this will balance the supply and demand side for residential real estate market.

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